

INFORMATION FLOW OF THE PRESENT TIME AND ITS INFLUENCE ON ADOLESCENT PSYCHOLOGY

Ismoilova Gulmira Erkin qizi
Student of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: The article describes the rapid penetration and development of computers networks in modern human life and activity, their special role in solving social, economic and even political problems of society, as well as the impact of pedagogical and psychological characteristics, knowledge, worldview. information about.

Keywords: Information, internet, technology, virtual, cybersecurity, threat, internet culture.

Studying the world experience in the years of independence, the life of society and the state in order to modernize and introduce innovative developments to it a lot of attention is paid to the issue of computerization at the level of state policy.

Humanity's flow of information has accelerated, the mood of the Earth's inhabitants, it is capable of changing one's psyche, goals and aspirations, and moreover, the whole way of thinking We are living in an age of information technology. This is the present Peoples, countries, states are a unique achievement of modern civilization to bring closer their mutual relations, world socio-political processes to management, worldly mood, worldly spirit and creation of profession is a miraculous event that serves.

However, it is such a huge, large-scale and brilliant achievement of civilization Who is using it for what purposes? What is his incomparable and powerful power? "is it working?" is becoming a problem.

In general, human thinking is expanding, science and technology are progressing as it accelerates, humanity shows its great creative power is doing. At the same time, he is a headache and a threat to his life he is also facing situations that abstract his perspective.

About three million years before the invention of writing, human communication was oral if he did, he learned to print books on an industrial basis only a thousand years later. From him Five hundred years later, he got telephone, radio and television. Traditional audio-visual and it took only fifty years to switch from tools to computers. This historical fact is the development of human thinking, the development of science and technology shows the dynamics of universal changes with The emergence of

computers has turned the entire globe into a single information space changed, as a result, with the fate of each country and the fate of the whole world a related reality has emerged.

The whole of Uzbekistan has become an active subject of this single information system. His connection with the world, his participation in world socio-political processes, interstate relations, political, economic, social, legal and cultural relations worldwide is implemented as part of the information system. This is direct email, electronic in solving both national and world problems through the information exchange system increasing efficiency, saving time, reducing financial costs decrease, moreover, it shows the potential of modern information exchange has a great effect.

However, this process is not without a number of problems. Including the world low level of use of the information system (5%), wide Internet system its underdevelopment and low level of use are evident.

But there is another side to the matter. This is direct information from the market what information to receive when using, from what information it also requires the capacity to use it. He lived and created in the period when modern technology development is just beginning the reason for the system of "man-technology" relations in the scientific works of some authors and that the consequences are not just discussed, the results of this process are psychological attempts to think about how it can be explained it can be observed that it is increasing. For example, between a person and a car psychological based on the impact of technology on the human psyche in relationships from some comments about the mechanisms of the Italian philosopher R. Guardini He studied at the Munich Technical School in 1959 on the topic "Machine and Man". report can be included among such works 1. Guardini in this lecture predicting that machines will take an increasingly large place in human life negative and positive aspects of the processes in the social, economic and spiritual spheres analyzes. According to R. Guardini: "in the relationship between man and technology The main cause of psychological stress in a person is the human being hidden in the expansion of his rule". Philosopher's tools are a person's that a hand will come to exercise dominion over nature and other people emphasizing, at the same time, to increase the level of responsibility of any authority draws attention. In his opinion, technology is behind the possibility of domination Not every person is ready for increased responsibility and that's why mental tension may arise in this system of relationships. A player pretending to be a virtual character hits another character, can kill. In this, he uses many types of weapons and realizes aggression and brutality. Aggressive games This is the main idea in its content.

Computer games after a certain amount, the child can use a real weapon, asocial behavior it is not a fact. Perhaps the gaming computer world is by a child Adequate perception, but certain behavior during the game impulses and skills are formed. Any signal from the outside world may cause their realization. The negative consequences of computer games are, first of all, physical related to health. In particular, the appearance of images in computer graphics, as well as posture, muscle tension and deformation of the spine and extreme obesity-related problems arise. It is mentioned above Although phenomena are observed in most people, the tendency of their occurrence he himself is a danger. The appearance of these effects to show that a person's time spent on the game decreases as a preventive measure possible On one of the popular sites dedicated to computer games:

Computer The game is a computer program that organizes the game process, partners in the game serves to connect or become a partner. Video games and mobile games are also considered computer games. Modern computer games it is recognized as one of the fields of art along with theater, cinema and so on The game is one of the fundamental concepts of culture. Virtual It is no coincidence that the most popular field of use of reality is games, of course: interactivity is the most important feature of any game, and the computer is its provides an ideal technical basis for its realization. Modern computer An important feature of these games is that these games are between a computer and a person not games between different people using a computer. Networkedas there are games, there are also special "entertainment centers". And so, the player stops being socially isolated. Virtual games are the new social is gaining an aspect. Games engage the participant in a constructed world allows you to move - any popular computer game is a private space nature, artificial history and passage of time, original philosophy, ethics and will have morals. When we observe people playing computer games, it is from shocks or Try to dodge the fire of virtual enemies we can see the actions. Sometimes fear, anger towards the virtual world, joy and similar emotions are evident. In other words, in the virtual world of computer games, when the player playing a computer game begins to feel what is happening as a real experience the participation effect begins. Also, behavior in the virtual world and this world a valuable and meaningful system is formed for him, that is, his psychic at all levels begins to reflect and ensures the formation of a person's virtual personality, that is "I am virtual". This completely takes the child out of reality. The child to the Internet before teaching, it is necessary to explain its benefits and harms. One in particular on the other hand, it is unique in the system of social values in historical conditions that transformations are taking place, and on the other hand, who cares about the future that

every country considers the reaching of young adults as the highest goal there is a high possibility that it will have a negative effect on the spiritual and spiritual development of a person scientific study of the phenomenon of addiction to computer games, even when learning learning as much as possible from the initial period when such a risk begins to arise is very relevant.

Today, "cyber security" is combined with information security around the world. concept is widely used and its importance is being recognized more and more. Cyber security - all the organizers of cyberspace (i.e. technical devices and users) from any threats and unexpected effects is a set of protection status. Developing a cyber security information society one of the important conditions in the process. Information security and cyber security the difference between the concepts is that the goal of information security is all confidentiality, integrity and availability of information in directions is to provide. Cybersecurity, on the other hand, is only in cyberspace (i.e to ensure security in the Internet network, information systems, etc.). focused strategies, security principles and guarantees and measures and tools implemented through human resources In short, cyber security is related to the fight against cybercrime it can be called a set of measures. The concept of cybercrime is information communication includes many types of crimes in the field of technology combined. Threats, viruses and other malicious software in the virtual network, preparation and distribution of illegal information, mass distribution of e-mails (spam), hacking, illegal access to websites, fraud, authorship violation of the right, as well as various other offenses are among them.

At this point, a legitimate question arises: what is the best way to combat cybercrime? Is there an effective tool? Go! This is Internet culture. Internet culture is the Internet is the culture of communication, information acquisition and transmission of users. Internet culture (also called cyberculture) also means in a virtual network negative impact on social consciousness, i.e. destructive, moral standards from inaccurate and biased informationconscious of use is understood to be restricted It should be noted that today's crimes that are common in the Internet world, including ideological and technical (hacking) violations by criminals and caused by the victims' non-observance of the norms of Internet culture is coming. Internet culture not only in the country, but also on a global scale effective fight against cybercrime only through development possible.

The following proposals for the development of Internet culture in society can be cited:

1. To approach the upbringing of children in the family with great responsibility;

2. Computer literacy to parents or their substitutes and Teaching the culture of using the Internet and through them the Internet of young people ensure their correct and effective use;

3. Improvement of legislation in the field of Internet security;

4. To improve Internet culture and information security skills in the minds of young people development of targeted manuals;

5. Educational institutions should adhere to the Internet culture when using the Internet, including, compliance with the standards of etiquette is ideological in their minds organization of educational seminars and events aimed at strengthening immunity to be done;

6. Publication of materials related to Internet culture in mass media to go;

7. Special prohibition programs against the reception of unwanted information on the computer installation. This kind of experience is widespread abroad (the most in this direction). popular programs: Cyberpatrol or Kidskontrol);

Modern psychologists, pedagogues, information-communication and computer scientists paying special attention to the role of technology in personal development various negative situations of the next generation, i.e. addiction to the Internet, computer Forgetting about real life tasks, getting caught up in games, social networks are negative work on current issues aimed at preventing the consequences and adolescents in more educational, developmental, language and other areas it is necessary to introduce methods of using educational programs. For example, Correct use of the useful information they need in the Internet world capacities should be formed. The positive that the modern Internet offers along with information resources, some virtual world dirt, information promoting corruption, computer games with negative impact protection of children and adolescents from dangerous effects has become an urgent issue managed to Internet resources are provided by experts in various fields, including pedagogical and it is necessary to control from a psychological point of view. In this regard, especially parents it is necessary to use computer programs that perform control. That's why forming immunity to protect themselves from misleading information of the growing generation in general education schools and other educational institutions is an important task of adults. Information and communication technology tools innovative that needs to be used in the food system while attracting teenagers creation of psychological-pedagogical programs is the demand of the times.

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